

THE INFLUENCE OF ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT IN MEDIATING LEADERSHIP STYLE ON EMPLOYEE ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR IN THE ERA OF BUREAUCRATIC REFORM: A QUANTITATIVE STUDY

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Abstract

The era of bureaucratic reform in Indonesia has triggered significant changes in human resource management in the public sector. This study aims to examine the mediating role of organizational commitment in the relationship between leadership style and employee organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). OCB, which includes voluntary and extra-role behaviors, becomes essential to improve organizational effectiveness during this period of change. This study uses a quantitative survey method with a simple random sampling technique of 153 employees in West Sulawesi Provincial government agencies who are undergoing a bureaucratic reform process. Data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using SmartPLS path analysis with result analysis using SmartPLS structural equation modeling. The results show that an effective leadership style has a positive and significant impact on employees' OCB, which in turn increases their OCB levels. In addition, organizational commitment proves to be a strong mediator in the relationship between leadership styles and OCB. These findings underscore the importance of leaders who can build strong organizational commitments to encourage positive behaviors outside of formal duties. The practical implications of this study include the need for leadership development that can inspire and strengthen organizational commitment to support the success of bureaucratic reform.

Keywords: Organizational Commitment, Leadership Style, Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), Bureaucratic Reform.

INTRODUCTION

The era of bureaucratic reform in Indonesia has brought about significant changes to governance and human resource management in the public sector. The main goal of this reform was to create an efficient, transparent, accountable, and public service-oriented bureaucracy. To achieve this goal, various aspects need to be changed, including the behavior of civil servants (Dwiyanto, 2021b, 2021a). One of the behaviors that is considered important in this context is Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) (Mathieu, 2021), which is voluntary behavior that goes beyond formal tasks and contributes positively to the organization (Podsakoff et al., 2003; Podsakoff & Organ, 1986; Özbek et al., 2024).

The concept of organizational commitment has been an interesting topic in the field of organizational behavior for decades. Organizational commitment refers to the extent to which employees feel emotionally connected, identified, and engaged with the organization in which they work. This concept was first introduced by (Becker, 1960) and since then it has since been the main focus of various studies on human resource behavior and management.

Research has shown that organizational commitment has a significant impact on various aspects of employee behavior and performance. Employees with high

organizational commitment tend to perform better (Hermanto et al., 2024), have lower attendance rates, and are less likely to leave an organization. Organizational commitment is closely related to Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), which is voluntary behavior that goes beyond formal tasks and contributes positively to the organization (Li & Chen, 2023; Lo Presti et al., 2023).

However, while many studies support the importance of organizational commitment, some show mixed results. For example (Rahman & Karim, 2022), in some contexts, other factors such as job satisfaction, organizational culture, and employee engagement were found to be more dominant in influencing employee behavior and performance than organizational commitment.

Thus, understanding and managing organizational commitment is an important aspect in efforts to increase organizational effectiveness and success (Porter et al., 2006; Stouten & Liden, 2020), especially in the context of bureaucratic reform in the public sector. Leadership development that can build strong organizational commitment can be key to encouraging positive behavior and improving employee performance (Rubim et al., 2020).

OCB includes various aspects, such as helping colleagues, being proactive, maintaining a conducive work environment (Porter et al., 2006; Choi et al., 2024; Hermanto et al., 2024; Rahman & Karim, 2022), and showing loyalty and dedication to the organization (Hermanto et al., 2024). This behavior not only improves individual performance, but also overall organizational performance (Özbek et al., 2024). However, to encourage OCB among employees, effective leadership and strong organizational commitment are required (Hermanto et al., 2024; Lei et al., 2023; Thomas & Albishri, 2024).

Leadership is a key factor affecting employee behavior and performance. Effective leaders can provide the direction, motivation, and support needed by employees to achieve organizational goals (Al Halbusi et al., 2023; Hermanto et al., 2024; Kusuma et al., 2024). In addition, leaders who can build good relationships with employees and create a positive work environment can increase organizational commitment (Spain, 2019; Lei et al., 2023; Thomas & Albishri, 2024). Organizational commitment, which reflects the extent to which employees feel connected and identified with the organization, is an important factor in driving OCB (Stouten & Liden, 2020; Hermanto et al., 2024; Lei et al., 2023).

Several studies have examined the relationship between leadership, organizational commitment, and OCB. For example, research by (Podsakoff et al., 2000; Hermanto et al., 2024; Choi et al., 2024; Lei et al., 2023; Thomas & Albishri, 2024) found that transformational leadership has a significant positive influence on OCB through increased organizational commitment. This research shows that leaders who are able to inspire and motivate employees to go beyond their personal interests for the sake of the organization can increase employee commitment and proactive behavior.

Research by (Meyer et al. (2002) and Hermanto et al. (2024) also emphasize the importance of organizational commitment as a mediator in the relationship between leadership and OCB. They found that effective leadership can increase organizational commitment, which encourages employees to engage in extra-role behaviors that benefit the organization.

In Indonesia, research conducted by Hermanto et al. (2024) showed that transparent and accountable leadership in the era of bureaucratic reform significantly increases organizational commitment and employee OCB. Found that in the context of bureaucratic reform, effective leaders can create a supportive work environment, which in turn encourages employees to demonstrate OCB behavior.

However, not all studies support these findings. Research by (Kusum et al. (2024a). Hreportedrtedd hreported) has presented different results. In her study, (found that transactional leadership was found to have a more significant influence than transformational leadership on OCB, but organizational commitment did not play a strong mediator. In some cases, an organization's commitment does not show a significant relationship with OCB. This study suggests that other factors, such as organizational culture and the work environment, may be more dominant in influencing OCB.

In **addition**, research by (Choi et al., 2024) found that in some government agencies, organizational commitment does not mediate the relationship between leadership and OCB. Factors such as job satisfaction and employee involvement were more influential in increasing OCB than organizational commitment was. These findings suggest that contextualization- and organization-specific conditions are crucial for understanding these dynamics.

This study examined the mediating role of organizational commitment in the relationship between leadership and OCB in the era of bureaucratic reform. By understanding how leadership and organizational commitment affect OCB, we hope that more in-depth insights can be gained on how to improve employee performance and the success of bureaucratic reform. This research is expected to contribute both theoretically and practically to the field of human resource management and bureaucratic reform in the West Sulawesi Provincial Government.

LITERATUR REVIEW

Bureaucratic Reform

Bureaucratic reform is an effort made by the government to increase the efficiency, transparency, accountability, and responsiveness of bureaucracy to the needs of the community. This reform aimed to overcome various problems that often hinder bureaucratic performance, such as corruption, inefficiency, and non-transparency. In the academic literature, bureaucratic reform has become an interesting topic for many researchers and practitioners who examine various aspects and approaches to improve the quality of bureaucracy.

Bureaucratic reform can be defined as a series of systematic and planned changes to the bureaucratic structure, processes, and work culture to improve the performance, effectiveness, and accountability of public services. According to Gaebler (1993), bureaucratic reform involves transforming traditional rigid and process-oriented bureaucracy into flexible and result-oriented bureaucracy. Bureaucratic reforms typically include several dimensions.

Organizational Restructuring: Changing the organizational structure to eliminate overlapping functions, reduce hierarchies, and improve coordination between units.

Human Resource Management: Develop a meritocracy-based recruitment, promotion, and training system to improve the quality and competence of employees.

Work process improvement: Information and communication technology is adopted to speed up administrative processes and improve the accessibility of public services.

Accountability and Transparency: Implement strict oversight and evaluation mechanisms to ensure efficient and responsible resource use.

(Gaebler 1993): The Entrepreneurial Government Approach. In their book "Reinventing Government," Osborne and Gaebler proposed the concept of entrepreneurial government, in which bureaucracy is encouraged to be more innovative, efficient, and responsive to the needs of society. They argue that bureaucracy should focus on outcomes rather than processes, give more autonomy to bureaucratic units, and encourage partnerships between the private sector and civil society.

(Hughes, 2017): New Public Management (NPM). Hughes, in his book "Public Management and Administration," discusses the New Public Management paradigm, which emphasizes the importance of efficiency, effectiveness, and market orientation in public administration. According to Hughes, NPM offers a practical approach to bureaucratic reform through the application of private-sector management techniques, decentralization, and increased competitiveness.

Public management reform (Pollitt & Bouckaert, 2000) Pollitt and Bouckaert in "Public Management Reform: A Comparative Analysis" emphasize the importance of context in the implementation of bureaucratic reform. They argued that bureaucratic reform must be adapted to the political, economic, and social conditions of each country. The one-size-fits-all approach is ineffective, and reforms must consider the organization's culture and existing value systems.

(Dwiyanto, 2021b) Bureaucratic Reform in Indonesia. In the Indonesian context, Dwiyanto underlined the unique challenges faced in bureaucratic reform such as corruption, nepotism, and fragmented bureaucracy. Dwiyanto proposed the need for a holistic approach that includes institutional capacity building, strengthening of the legal system, and active community participation in the reform process.

In Indonesia, bureaucratic reform has been implemented through various initiatives, such as restructuring the organizational structure, improving the human resource management system, and strengthening the supervision and evaluation mechanisms. Despite facing great challenges, these reforms have shown progress in several respects, such as improving the quality of public services and transparency.

Bureaucratic reform is a complex and multidimensional process that requires a holistic contextual approach. Expert views and international case studies show that successful reforms require strong commitment from governments, implementation of information technology, effective human resource management, and active participation of the community. In Indonesia, despite still facing various challenges, bureaucratic reform has shown significant progress, and continuous efforts are needed to achieve more efficient, transparent, and responsive bureaucracy.

Leadership Style

Leadership style is a key element in organizational management and plays an important role in influencing employee performance and motivation. Leadership style refers to the behaviors and approaches used by leaders to interact with their

subordinates. Researchers have identified various leadership styles, each with its own strengths and weaknesses.

Leadership style is a consistent pattern of behavior used by leaders to influence, direct, and motivate subordinates. The leadership style reflects how leaders make decisions, communicate, and handle conflicts.

Transformational leadership is a style of leadership in which the leader inspires and motivates employees to achieve higher goals and to make positive changes in the organization.

1. Idealized Influence: Leaders are respected and trusted role models.
2. Inspirational Motivation: Leaders provide an attractive vision and motivate employees to achieve it.
3. Intellectual Stimulation: Leaders encourage employees to think creatively and innovatively.
4. Individualized Consideration: Leaders pay attention to the individual needs and development of employees.

The transactional leadership style focuses on exchanges between leaders and subordinates where employees are rewarded for their performance.

1. Contingent Reward: Leaders provide rewards in accordance with the achievement of targets.
2. Active Management by Exception: Leaders actively monitor performance and take corrective action before problems occur.
3. Passive Management by Exception: Leaders only intervene when standards are not met or problems arise.

In the laissez-faire leadership style, leaders give employees complete freedom to make decisions and carry out their duties without interference.

1. Lack of intervention and support from leaders and employees leads to high autonomy.

(Burns et al., 1978) Transformational and Transactional leadership styles: the concept of transformational and transactional leadership styles. He described transformational leaders as individuals who inspire their followers to go beyond personal interests to achieve greater goals, while transactional leaders are more focused on exchanging rewards and sanctions based on performance.

(Bass & Bass Bernard, 1985) Transformational and Transactional Models: Bass further developed Burns' concept and developed a model of transformational and transactional leadership styles. Bass emphasized the importance of transformational leadership styles in improving employee motivation and performance and developing specific dimensions of these two leadership styles.

Lewin identified three main leadership styles: autocratic, democratic and laissez-faire (Lewin et al. 1939). The autocratic style is characterized by centralized decision-making; the democratic style involves employee participation in decision-making; and the laissez-faire style gives employees complete freedom.

(House, 1971) Path-Goal Theory: House developed a path-goal theory that states that leaders must adapt their leadership style to the situation and needs of subordinates in order to achieve maximum effectiveness. Leadership styles can vary from directive, supportive, participatory, to achievement-oriented styles.

Leadership style has a significant impact on organizational effectiveness and employee well-being. Transformational leadership styles, with their focus on individual inspiration and development, are often associated with more positive outcomes than transactional and laissez-faire leadership styles. Experts such as Burns, Bass, and Lewin have made important contributions to our understanding of how leadership styles affect employee behavior and performance. Empirical research supports the idea that leaders who are able to adapt their style to the needs and situations of subordinates tend to achieve better results in the long run.

Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment is an important concept in the fields of human resource management and organizational behavior. It refers to the extent to which an employee feels emotionally, psychologically, and professionally attached to the organization for which they work. Organizational commitment is often associated with a variety of positive outcomes such as improved employee performance, higher job satisfaction, and decreased turnover rates.

Organizational commitment can be defined as the psychological state that binds an employee to their organization, which reduces their likelihood of leaving the organization. Meyer and Allen (1991) developed the most widely used model of organizational commitment, which identifies three main components: affective, ongoing, and normative commitment.

Affective Commitment: An employee's emotional attachment to the organization. Employees with high affective commitment feel happy to be part of the organization and tend to work harder because they care about it. According to Meyer and Allen, affective commitment develops through positive experiences and organizational support.

Continuity Commitment: relates to employee awareness of the costs associated with leaving the organization. This includes an assessment of personal investments such as time and effort, as well as available job alternatives. Employees with a high level of ongoing commitment remain in the organization because they feel that leaving the organization will cause great losses.

Normative Commitment: a feeling of obligation to stay in an organization. They often stem from social norms, professional ethics, or personal loyalty. Employees with high normative commitment feel that they should stick to the organization because it is the right thing to do.

The three-component model (Meyer & Allen, 1991) proposes a three-component model of organizational commitment that includes affective, continuous, and normative commitments. They argue that employees who have strong affective commitment are more motivated to achieve organizational goals, while ongoing and normative commitment are more related to long-term loyalty.

The one-dimensional Model (Mowday et al. 1974) proposes that organizational commitment can be measured as a one-dimensional model that reflects the level of

employee engagement with the organization. They emphasize the importance of identifying employees with organizational goals and values.

Side-Bet Theory: (Becker, 1960), developed the "side-bet" theory which states that organizational commitment is the result of an investment made by employees, which makes them reluctant to leave the organization because they have invested a lot in it. This commitment is more oriented towards gains and losses than toward emotional connections.

Organizational Commitment Questionnaire (OCQ): Mowday et al. (1979) developed the OCQ to measure organizational commitment as an attitude. They suggest that organizational commitment involves a strong desire to remain a member of the organization, a desire to work behalf of the organization, and the acceptance of the organization's values and goals.

Organizational commitment is an important and multidimensional concept that affects various work outcomes and employee behaviors. The three-component model developed by Meyer and Allen provides a comprehensive framework for understanding how emotional attachment, cost awareness, and sense of obligation contribute to employee commitment to the organization. Empirical research supports the importance of affective commitment in producing positive work outcomes, and shows that organizational support plays an important role in building this commitment.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is an important concept in the field of organizational behavior, which refers to the voluntary actions of employees that are not directly recognized by the formal reward system, but contribute to the effectiveness of the organization. This concept was first introduced by Organ (1988) and has been the subject of many studies examining various factors that influence OCB.

According to Organ (1988), OCB includes actions such as helping colleagues, protecting organizational resources, and working with extra enthusiasm and effort.

Altruism: Voluntary behavior to help colleagues or others in an organization with work-related tasks or problems. Example: Helping a colleague who is overloaded.

Conscientiousness: The level of employee compliance with organizational rules and policies that exceed minimum expectations. Example: arriving on time and adhering to a strict work schedule.

Sportsmanship: a willingness to tolerate discomfort or difficulty without complaining. Example: Not complaining when facing a work situation that is not ideal or when having to work overtime.

Courtesy: Behaviors that prevent work problems by helping and paying attention to the needs of others. Example: Providing necessary information to colleagues to prevent problems.

Civic Virtue: Involvement in organizational activities that reflects active participation and responsibility as a member of the organization. Examples include attending volunteer meetings and participating in discussions to help the organization.

The foundational Concept (Organ, 1988) pioneered the development of the OCB concept. He emphasized that OCB is a voluntary behavior that is not formally expected, but contributes to the effectiveness of the organization. The organ also

identified five main dimensions of OCB: Altruism, conscientiousness, sportsmanship, courtesy, and civic virtue.

Antecedents and Consequences: Podsakoff et al. (2000) developed a model that identifies a variety of factors that affect OCB, including job satisfaction, organizational fairness, and leadership style. They also highlight the positive consequences of OCB, such as improved team performance and customer satisfaction.

Bateman and OCB (1983) show that there is a positive relationship between job Satisfaction and OCB. They argue that employees who are satisfied with their jobs are more likely to engage in voluntary behavior that benefits the organization.

Role Theory and OCB (Katz & Kahn, 2015) contribute to the understanding of OCB through role theory, which states that extra-role behaviors such as OCB are essential for organizational effectiveness. They classified these behaviors as innovative and spontaneous actions that go beyond formal job descriptions.

OCB is a voluntary behavior critical to the effectiveness and success of an organization. Through various dimensions, such as altruism, conscientiousness, sportsmanship, courtesy, and civic virtue, OCB contributes to a positive and productive work environment. Research has shown that OCB is influenced by factors such as job satisfaction, organizational fairness, and leadership style. Experts such as Organ, Podsakoff, and Bateman have made significant contributions to the understanding and development of the concept of OCB, which continues to be an important focus in organizational behavior research.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sample and Data Collection

The research design adopted for this study is explanatory research, namely causality, which explains the relationship between selected research through hypothesis testing (Ghozali, 2006). There were three variables: leadership style, organizational commitment, and OCB. Data collection was conducted using the observation method, interviews, and closed questionnaires, which included four parts. The first section is reserved for general information of the respondents. The remaining three parts included questions related to the mediating role of organizational commitment. Data were collected from the West Sulawesi Provincial Government. The reliability of the instrument was carried out through a pilot study of 50 respondents as a means to check that the questions function as intended and understood by people who are likely to respond to them and to reduce sampling errors and improve the response rate of the questionnaire and the score for Alpha Cronbach is < 0.5 . The trial showed that random sampling was best for this study because our questionnaire was easy for our target respondents to understand. After that, data collection began on a large scale, 200 questionnaires were distributed, of which 165 were re-accepted, and seven questionnaires were removed from the analysis due to a lack of information provided. Therefore, the response rate in the present study was 65.1%. The sample of employees was chosen to improve the accuracy of the results because the number of employees within the West Sulawesi Provincial Government is more than 2209 employees. The questionnaire included 40 items related to leadership style, organizational commitment, and OCB. Therefore, based on the modeling of structural equations, the sample size should be 10 times that of the items used in the study. To better understand the respondents' insights, we opened up an information space for

them and tried to collect more responses. The distribution of permanent lecturers in the West Sulawesi Provincial Government is quite large and to narrow the achievement of the number of samples by using the proportional random sampling stratified technique based on the Slovin formula (Umar, 2001) to attract the number of samples so that the number is *representative*; therefore, this study involved a sample size (N = 153).

Measurement Scale

Leadership styles, judged by 16 items, were drawn from previous studies (Bass & Avolio, 1994; Yukl, 2013). This scale was adopted because it has been used successfully in previous studies (Al Halbusi et al., 2023; Batool et al., 2024; Hermanto et al., 2024; Hsieh et al., 2024; Kusuma et al., 2024; Qalati et al., 2022). Organizational Commitment was assessed using a nine-item scale adopted from the study (Allen & Meyer, 1990; Meyer & Allen, 1991; Williams & Anderson, 1991; Podsakoff & Organ, 1986) and successfully developed in recent studies (Choi et al., 2024; Hermanto et al., 2024; Lei et al., 2023; Thomas & Albishri, 2024). Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) was evaluated using 15 items drawn from previous studies (Organ, 1988; Podsakoff et al., 2000; Williams & Anderson, 1991). This scale was adopted because its reliability has been reported in previous studies (Hermanto et al., 2024; Hsieh et al., 2024; Kusuma et al., 2024; Lo Presti et al., 2023; Qalati et al., 2022; Rahman & Karim, 2022). All variants were rated on a Likert scale rating of 5 points 1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree.

Table 1: Respondent Characteristics. Demographic Characteristics of Work Units

Respondent Work Unit	Sum	Percentage (%)
Provincial Secretariat Office	42	27
Many	5	3
Inspectorate	1	1
City	35	23
Secretariat of the House of Representatives	1	1
District Government	69	45
Total	153	100

Source: West Sulawesi Provincial Government, 2021.

Analysis

The results and models were analyzed using partial least squares, consistent PLS algorithm techniques, and bootstrapping. Structural equation modeling was used for the path analysis. The measurement models were tested and verified on the basis of the reliability and validity of the variables recorded in the latest research. The inferential and descriptive results are reported in the tables. The main reasons for SmartPLS include its popularity and widespread acceptance of its application (Hair et al., 2015; Hair & Latan, 2012). Furthermore, PLS is considered to be more convenient and is one of the systems developed (McDonald, 1996). However, this study involved mediation and moderation effects, which are the main objectives of using this software (Ringle et al., 2015). Most scholars have recently preferred SmartPLS in all disciplines (Camilleri, 2024; Chakraborty et al., 2024; Hauff et al., 2024; Joana Carolina et al., 2024; Robina-Ramírez et al., 2024; Shomotova et al., 2024).

MEASUREMENT RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The study used a single factor Harman test and a full collinearity test to ensure that the data were free of common method biases. The results of the Harman single-factor test showed that the single factor explained only 24.221% of the total variance, which was well below 50.0% (Podsakoff et al., 2003). In addition, following the latest suggestions in the PLS-SEM literature (Kock & Hadaya, 2018), this study uses a full collinearity approach, specifically the variance inflation factor (VIF), to detect evidence of CMB. The results shown in Table 2 indicate that CMB is not the main concern because the calculated VIF is less than three (Hair et al., 2011). Again, following previous research (Sharma & Fatima, 2024), the current work concludes that because of a study examining the existence of mediation effects, it is very difficult for the respondents to manipulate ethical behavior. Therefore, concerns about CMB are minimal; therefore, in this analysis, the potential for CMB is low.

Before moving towards the analysis, the study used the recommended Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) to measure the adequacy of sampling and to ensure the suitability of the data. The KMO test result is 0.828, which is greater than the acceptable threshold of 0.50; hence, it is considered substantial for explanatory factor analysis (Çetinkaya and Karabulut, 2016; Chan, 2019). In addition, the results of the Bartlett test reflect a significance level of 0.000, and are thus considered good because they are below the significance level of 0.05. No research items were removed from the model because the loading factor was less than 0.7, as Hair et al. (2011) suggested.

Measurement Model

Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) was used to analyze the results. Several tests were conducted to determine reliability, validity, and path coefficients. In addition, to ensure that data are free from multicollinearity, bias related to other data was measured (Hais Jr et al., 2010). The analysis section uses a two-way approach to assess the results. 1) Evaluation of measurement models and 2) structural models (Hais Jr. et al., 2010).

1) Measurement Model Assessment

According to Henseler and Fassott (2010), suggestions to measure the model in this study are needed to assess "individual item reliability, internal consistency, content validity, convergent validity, and discriminatory validity."

Reliability of individual items: Assessed through the external loading of items associated with a specific dimension (Hair, Sarstedt, Pieper, et al., 2012; Sarstedt et al., 2016), it is recommended that it should be maintained within 0.40 and 0.70. As shown in Table 2, all grades are satisfactory and meet the standard, and the study items are currently maintained between 0.469 and 0.818.

According to a study by Chin et al. (2003), Cronbach's alpha (CA) should be greater than 0.7. The CA value was maintained between 0.721 and 1,000. Therefore, this study adequately meets the standards of action reliability.

Internal consistency reliability (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988) proposes that the composite reliability (CR) value should be equal to or exceed 0.7. Table 2 shows the CR of the construct, which was maintained between 0.772 and 1,000, indicating adequate action reliability.

Convergent validity: According to Fornell and Larcker (1981), the rule of thumb for AVE values should be equivalent to 0.5 or more. The AVE value of the study was maintained between 0.557 and 0.732 in the future, and it was concluded that this study met the requirements for a satisfactory level of convergent validity.

Validity of discrimination: Two methods are used to evaluate the "validity of the discrimination" of variables. It is ensured that the cross-loading indicator should be higher than that of other opposing constructions (Hair, Sarstedt, Pieper, et al., 2012). 2) According to the criterion (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), the square root of the AVE for each construct must exceed the inter-correlation of the construct with the construct of the other model". Therefore, as shown in Table 2, it can be concluded that all constructs used in this study have an adequate level of discriminatory validity.

2) Structural Model Assessment

This study used PLS bootstrapping with 5000 bootstraps and 153 cases with motives to analyze the hypothetical model and its significance (Henseler et al., 2009). Figure 1 shows a comprehensive illustration of the structural model assessment along with statistics related to the moderation of spiritual leadership styles.

Structural model collinearity problem: To ascertain the multicollinearity problem, this study required the heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) ratio (Gold et al., 2001), which proposes that the construct value should not exceed 0.9. Table 4 shows that the maximum value of the construct was 0.775; therefore, for the next time this study is free from the problem of multicollinearity.

Table 2: Evaluation of Measurement Model

Construct	Items code	Loadings	CA ¹	CR ²	AVE ³	Inner VIF
Leadership Style (LD)			0,804	0,772	0,515	1,113
	X1.1	0,658				
	X1.2	0,580				
	X1.3	0,469				
	X1.4	0,624				
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)	X1.5	0,818				
			0,721	0,806	0,855	
	Y1.1	0,666				
	Y1.2	0,632				
	Y1.3	0,751				
Organizational Commitment (OC)	Y1.4	0,644				
	Y1.5	0,674				
			0,787	0,824	0,610	1,049
	Z1.1	0,775				
Moderating LD*OC -> OCB	Z1.2	0,792				
	Z1.3	0,775				
	LD * OC	0,791	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,071

Figure 1: Modeling of Structural Equations (Path Coefficients and p-values)

Table 3: Discriminant Validity Coefficient

Constructs	LD	Moderating LD*OC -> OCB	OC	OCB
LD	0,561			
Moderating LD*OC -> OCB	0,242	1,000		
OC	0,197	0,039	0,781	
OCB	0,391	0,055	0,647	0,675

Table 4: Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT)

Constructs	LD	Moderating LD*OC -> OCB	OC	OCB
LD				
Moderating LD*OC -> OCB	0,458			
OC	0,396	0,235		
OCB	0,596	0,134	0,775	

Coefficient of determination To evaluate the variance of the construct, PLS-SEM evaluates the coefficient of R², which is also called the coefficient of determination (Hair et al., 2011). According to Cohen (2013), R² values of 0.60, 0.33 and 0.19 are set as a rule of thumb, and these values are described as substantial, moderate, and weak. Hair et al. (2010) proposed that the R² coefficient is subject to the situation in which a particular study was conducted.

However, as per Falk and Miller (1992), the recommendation of an R² coefficient of 0.10 is also acceptable. As shown in Table 6, this study recorded an R² value of 0.491. The value of 0.491 indicates that an OCB variation of 50.9% occurs due to LD and Moderating Effect.

Model predictive relevance: Keeping in mind the reflective nature of the action, this study used the Q² cross-validated redundancy measure to evaluate the model, as suggested (Ringle et al., 2020). It is an indicator of the predictive power of out-of-sample models or the predictive relevance given by (Geisser 1974) and Ghazali and Latan (2015) Q² value. In the structural equation model, a Q² value greater than zero for a particular reflective endogenous latent variable indicates the predictive relevance of the path model for a given dependent construct. In addition, as a relative measure of predictive relevance, q² values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35, respectively, indicate that exogenous constructs have predictive relevance of small, medium, or substantial for

a given endogenous construct. Therefore, as shown in Table 6, the results indicate that the model has a moderate predictive relevance of 0.167.

Effect Size (f^2): To examine the R^2 value of all endogenous constructs, changes in the R^2 value when a particular exogenous construct is omitted from the model can be used to evaluate whether the omitted construct has a substantive impact on the endogenous construct.

This size is preferred by editors and reviewers. Additionally, the values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35, respectively, represent small, medium, and large effects, respectively (Cohen, 2013). If the f^2 value is < 0.02 , it indicates that there is no effect. The results of the study, shown in Table 5, indicate that there is an effect.

Testing the moderation effect: The PLS-SEM product indicator technique was used to identify and assess the strength of the moderating effect of organizational commitment (OC) on the leadership style (LD) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) of employees (Chin et al., 2003). This study used the product indicator method because the recommended moderation construct is continuous (Rigdon et al., 2017). Cohen's (2013) rules were used to assess moderate effects.

Given H2, it is proposed that organizational commitment (OC) moderates the relationship between leadership style (LD) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). As shown in Table 5 and Figure 1 (moderating LD*OC \rightarrow OCB $\beta = 0.716$, t-value = 11.190) is significant. Therefore, H2 was fully supported.

Determining the strength of the moderating effect: The strength of the moderating effect can be evaluated by matching the R^2 values of the main model and the full R^2 (Henseler & Fassott, 2010), and the strength of the moderating effect can be assessed using the formula given below (Cohen, 2013):

$$\text{Effect Size } (f)^2 = \frac{R^2 \text{ model with moderator} - R^2 \text{ model without moderator}}{1 - R^2 \text{ model with moderator}}$$

Values of 0.02, 0.15 and 0.35, respectively represent weak, moderate, and strong moderating effects, respectively (Cohen, 2013). As per the rules (Cohen, 2013), the strength of the moderating effect of leadership style was assessed and is reported in Table 6. Chin et al. (2003) stated that small effect sizes do not necessarily mean that causal moderating effects are irrelevant. "Even small interaction effects can be meaningful under extreme moderate conditions; if the resulting beta changes are meaningful, then it is important to consider these conditions" (Chin et al., 2003). It has been recommended that the moderating role of organizational commitment (OC) over Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is strong at 0.491. The slope of the relationship between leadership style (LD) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) which is moderated by organizational commitment (OC) that the relationship is stronger when organizational commitment is a moderating variable.

Table 5: Path Coefficients and Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Relationship	Path coefficient	Mean	SD (STDEV)	t-value	Decision	f Square
Direct effect H1	LD -> OCB	0,271	0,284	0,070	3,843	Supported	0,129
H2	Moderating LD*OC -> OCB	0,716	0,809	0,084	11,190	Supported	0,802
H3	OC -> OCB	0,595	0,601	0,057	10,522	Supported	0,663

Notes: Critical values. *t-value > 1.96 ($p < 0.05$).

Table 6: Structural Model

Model	Construct cross-validated redundancy			Coefficient of determination		Goodness of fit (SRMR)
	SSO	SSE	Q ² (= 1-SSE/SSO)	R ²	Adj. R ²	
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)	765.000	673.021	0.167	0.491	0.481	0.136

The results showed that employees within the West Sulawesi Provincial Government with a good leadership style tended to have good organizational commitment. In summary, leadership style has a significant impact on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). The relationship between leadership style (LD) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is stronger when employees have high organizational commitment as employees in the West Sulawesi Provincial Government.

DISCUSSION

A survey-based quantitative study was used to describe the factors that affect the Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) of employees working in the West Sulawesi Provincial Government. The findings of this study are interesting, considering that the moderating role of organizational commitment (OC) has many different factors used in other Provincial Government Scopes, which can also be triggered regarding how they support Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), such as high OCB levels, helping colleagues, obeying rules, and showing politeness.

Leadership plays an important role in determining employee behavior and performance in an organization (Bass & Bass Bernard, 1985). One of the most desirable behaviors in organizations is Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), which is the voluntary behavior of employees beyond the demands of their formal work (Organ, 1988). This study aimed to analyze the direct influence of leadership style on the OCB of West Sulawesi government employees. Leadership style had a significant direct influence on OCB in West Sulawesi government employees' OCB (t-value = 3,843 > 1.96). This suggests that the higher the leadership style perceived by employees, the higher the level of OCB demonstrated (Bass & Avolio, 1994; Yukl, 2013). Transformational leadership proved to be the most effective in increasing OCB, followed by transactional leadership with a weaker influence, while laissez-faire leadership had a negative influence on OCB (Podsakoff et al., 2000). Leaders who can inspire, motivate, and support employees play an important role in encouraging behaviors that support organizational effectiveness and efficiency (Judge & Piccolo, 2004).

Transformational leadership is often associated with increased OCB, because transformational leaders can inspire and motivate employees to achieve more than expected (Podsakoff et al., 2000). Transformational leadership dimensions such as ideal influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration directly influence positive employee behavior, these findings are consistent with previous research (Al Halbusi et al., 2023; Batool et al., 2024; Hermanto et al., 2024; Hsieh et al., 2024; Kusuma et al., 2024; Qalati et al., 2022). A leadership style with a focus on individual inspiration and attention encourages employees to actively participate in activities that go beyond their job description and plays an important role in driving OCB.

The indirect Effect of leadership style on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) of West Sulawesi government employees, with organizational commitment as a mediating variable. An effective leadership style can increase organizational commitment, which, in turn, can affect employees' OCB (Podsakoff et al., 1996). Leadership styles, especially transformational leadership, are known to increase organizational commitment through inspiration, motivation, and individualized attention to employees (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Transformational leaders tend to motivate employees to go beyond their personal interests and contribute more to the organization (Judge & Piccolo, 2004). Leadership style has a significant influence on OCB among West Sulawesi government employees through the mediation of organizational commitment. Transformational leaders, with their ability to inspire and motivate, play a crucial role in increasing employees' affective commitment, which ultimately drives OCB. This study emphasizes the importance of effective leadership in building commitment and positive behavior in government organizations. In the context of government employees in West Sulawesi, understanding the indirect influence of leadership style on OCB through organizational commitment is very important to improve the performance and effectiveness of bureaucracy in the reform era.

Organizational commitment is an employee's emotional attachment to the organization, desire to remain a part of the organization, and sense of obligation to work hard for the success of the organization (Meyer & Allen, 1991; Mowday et al., 1979). Organizational commitment can mediate the relationship between leadership style and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) (Meyer et al., 2002). Path analysis shows that the direct effect of organizational commitment has a significant influence on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) (t-value = 10,522, > 1.96). The indirect effect of leadership style on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) through organizational commitment was significant (t-value = 11,190, p > 1.96).

The results show that organizational commitment plays a significant role as a mediator in the relationship between leadership style and OCB. Leadership style had a stronger indirect influence on OCB. Leaders who are able to increase affective commitment, sustainable commitment, and normative commitment of employees are more effective in encouraging OCB, the findings are supported by previous findings (Hermanto et al., 2024; Hsieh et al., 2024; Kusuma et al., 2024; Lo Presti et al., 2023; Qalati et al., 2022; Rahman & Karim, 2022). Leadership style has a significant indirect influence on OCB through organizational commitment among government employees in West Sulawesi. Transformational leadership, with a focus on inspiration and individual concern, has a stronger influence on organizational commitment and OCB. Transactional leadership, through rewards, also plays an important role in driving organizational commitment and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB).

CONCLUSION

To improve Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) among government employees in West Sulawesi, it is necessary to implement a leadership style that emphasizes shared vision, individual attention, and intellectual stimulation. In addition, a fair and transparent reward system is important for encouraging OCB. To improve Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) among government employees in West Sulawesi, organizations must develop a transformational leadership style that

emphasizes shared vision, individual attention, and intellectual stimulation. In addition, a fair and transparent reward system is important to increase organizational commitment and encourage OCB.

Organizational commitment plays an important role in mediating the influence of leadership style on OCB. Transformational leadership significantly increases employee affective commitment, which in turn increases Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). This indirect influence shows that effective leaders not only motivate employees directly, but also build strong emotional bonds with the organization, which encourages voluntary behavior. By adopting strategies that increase emotional attachment, job stability, and employee moral responsibility, another study emphasizes the importance of effective leadership styles in improving employees' Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) through increased organizational commitment. Leaders who can inspire, motivate, and support employees can create a conducive work environment for voluntary behavior that supports the success of effective and efficient organizations in the era of bureaucratic reform.

This study provides important insights into the direct influence of organizational commitment on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) among government employees in West Sulawesi. Although it has some limitations, the findings of this study contribute to the literature on organizational behavior and provide practical implications that can help improve the effectiveness and performance of bureaucracy in the reform era.

LIMITATIONS AND CONTRIBUTIONS

This study uses a quantitative approach with a survey method that may not capture the nuances and complexities of organizational commitment and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). Qualitative data obtained through questionnaires or case studies may provide more comprehensive insight.

The study was conducted only among government employees in West Sulawesi; therefore, the results may not be generalized to other geographical or organizational contexts in addition to the data collected through self-reported questionnaires, which are susceptible to social bias, where respondents may give answers that are considered socially desirable rather than those that reflect the actual reality.

This study may not fully control for disruptive variables, such as organizational culture, work climate, or other external factors that may affect the relationship between organizational commitment and OCB.

This study strengthens our understanding of how the three dimensions of organizational commitment (affective, sustainable, and normative) affect OCB. The results of this study support the theory (Meyer & Allen, 1991) and show its relevance in the context of government employees.

This study provides empirical evidence supporting the importance of organizational commitment in the context of bureaucratic reform. Policymakers can use these findings to design reform initiatives that focus not only on structure and processes, but also on strengthening employee commitment to the organization. By increasing OCB through strengthening organizational commitment, the quality of public services provided by government employees can be improved, thereby providing direct benefits to the community.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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